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DNA analyses of the Helgoland ‘Black-eared Wheatear’

We used a partial fragment (GenBank ID PX698936) of the mitochondrial gene NADH dehydrogenase subunit II (ND2) for species level identification through comparison with sequences published by Alaei Kakhki et al (2018). Total genomic DNA was extracted from a lost feather of the bird using the QIAamp DNA Micro Kit following the manufacturer’s instructions (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). A partial fragment of ND2 was amplified with polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using the primers MetL and ASNH (Tavares et al 2006). PCR reaction volumes were 25 µl containing 12.5 µl GoTaq Hot Start Green Master Mix (Promega), 2 µl genomic DNA, 2 µl of each primer with a concentration of 10 µM and 6.5 µl ddH₂O using a standard reaction protocol (Schweizer et al 2012) applying an annealing temperature of 52°C. PCR was done with a SensoQuest thermal cycler and sequencing was performed in both directions using PCR primers with Microsynth AG (Balgach, Switzerland).

Sequence alignment was performed using the MAFFT algorithm 7.450 (Katoh 2002, Katoh & Standley 2013) implemented as a plug-in in Geneious 2024.0.5 (www.geneious.com) using default settings. To infer species level identity based on a reconstruction of phylogenetic relationships of analysed samples, a maximum likelihood (ML) search was performed with PhyML 3.3.20180621 (Guindon et al 2010), again implemented as a plug-in in Geneious, with a sequence of Desert Wheatear *Oenanthe deserti* used as an outgroup (cf Alaei Kakhki et al 2023). Finally, branch support was assessed with 1000 bootstrap replicates.

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Western Black-eared Wheatear on Helgoland, Germany, in October 2002 and lessons for identification of autumn females

Figure 1: Maximum Likelihood Tree of *Oenanthe* taxa estimated using PhyML with bootstrap values >50 indicated at nodes. The *Oenanthe* from Helgoland is nested in robustly supported clade within *O hispanica*. GenBank accession numbers of sequences are given at beginning of labels.